

Chemical examination of *Citrus sinensis* roots variety Pineapple

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Abstract : Chemical examination of *Citrus sinensis* roots var. Pineapple has afforded six compounds which have been identified as tetracosane, ethyl pentacosanoate, tetratriacontanoic acid, tangertin, β -sitosteryl- β -D-glucopyranoside, 5,4'-dihydroxy-7,3'-dimethoxyflavanone-3-O- β -D-glucopyranoside. All these compounds have already been reported from the flavedo of this plant.

Keywords : *Citrus sinensis*, Pineapple, glucopyranoside.

Introduction

Citrus sinensis (L.) belongs to Rutaceae family and it is known as sweet orange¹. The variety which has flavour similar to that of pineapple has the distinct name *C. sinensis* var. Pineapple. The plant is known for its purgative, laxative and diuretic properties. It is useful against piles and enlargement of spleen². In absence of a report on the chemical components of its roots, we have taken up the present study for isolating and characterizing the various compounds from its root.

Experimental

Melting points were obtained from Ganson Electrical Melting Point Apparatus, ¹H NMR on Bruker AC 400F MHz NMR spectrophotometer, IR on Perkin-Elmer IR spectrophotometer and mass spectra on VG 70 S 11-250 J GCMS DS Mass spectrometer.

Roots (3 kg) were chopped into small pieces, dried in shade under a fan for 72 h and extracted with hot MeOH. Extractives were subjected to column chromatography using silica gel (60–120 mesh). Six compounds were isolated and characterized.

Compound A (Tetracosane, **1**) : It was obtained on elution with petroleum ether and crystallized from chloroform as a colourless solid, 15 mg, m.p. 51 °C (Lit.^{3,4} m.p. 49–51 °C); ¹H NMR (δ , CDCl₃) : 0.78 (6H, t, *J*

7.5 Hz, 2 \times Me), 1.18 (44H, br, 22 \times CH₂); GCMS : 338 (M⁺, 7%).

Compound B (Ethyl pentacosanoate, **2**) : It was obtained on elution with benzene petroleum ether (1 : 3) and crystallized from MeOH, 20 mg, m.p. 78 °C (Lit.^{4,5} m.p. 77.5 °C); ν_{\max} (nujol, cm⁻¹) : 1737 (CO); ¹H NMR (δ , CDCl₃) : 0.79 (3H, t, *J* 7.0 Hz, Me), 1.00–2.00 (47H, m, 22 \times CH₂, 1 \times Me), 2.25 (2H, t, *J* 7.0 Hz, CH₂-COO), 4.10 (2H, *J* 7.0 Hz, COOCH₂); GCMS (408, M⁺-2, 18%).

Compound C (Tetratriacontanoic acid, **3**) : It was obtained on elution with EtOAc-C₆H₆ (1 : 19) and crystallized from MeOH, 22 mg, m.p. 96 °C (Lit.^{4,6} m.p. 98.3–98.5 °C); ν_{\max} (nujol, cm⁻¹) : 1739 (CO); ¹H NMR (δ , CDCl₃) : 0.82 (3H, t, *J* 7.5 Hz, Me), 1.18–1.54 (62H, m, 31 \times CH₂), 2.10 (2H, t, CH₂COO); GCMS : 508 (M⁺, 14%).

Compound D (Tangertin, **4**) : It was obtained on elution with EtOAc-C₆H₆ (1 : 3) and crystallized from MeOH as a white solid, 28 mg, m.p. 153 °C (Lit.^{4,7} m.p. 154 °C); ν_{\max} (nujol, cm⁻¹) : 1680 (CO); ¹H NMR (δ , CDCl₃) : 7.59 (2H, dd, *J* 7.0, 1.9 Hz, H-2', H-6'), 7.38 (2H, dd, *J* 7.0, 1.9 Hz, H-3', H-5'), 6.80 (1H, s, H-3), 4.09, 4.03, 3.98 and 3.91 (3H, s, each OMe); GCMS : 410 (M⁺, 8%).

Compound E (β -Sitosterol- β -D-glucopyranoside, **5**) :

It was obtained on elution with EtOAc-C₆H₆ (1 : 1) and crystallized from EtOAc, 35 mg, m.p. 280 °C (Lit.^{4,8} m.p. 283–286 °C). It gave positive Liebermann-Burchard reaction. It responded to Molisch test. Its acetate had m.p. 170 °C (Lit.⁷ m.p. 171 °C).

Compound F (5,4'-Dihydroxy-7,3'-dimethoxyflavanone-3-O- β -D-glucopyranoside, **6**) : It was obtained with MeOH-EtOAc (1 : 9) and crystallized from EtOH, 85 mg, m.p. 210 °C (Lit.⁴ m.p. 210 °C). It gave green colour with alcoholic FeCl₃. It responded to colour reaction with Mg/HCl; ν_{\max} (nujol, cm⁻¹) : 1647 (CO); GCMS: 494 (M⁺, 3%); Killiani hydrolysis : glucose + 3,5,4'-trihydroxy-7,3'-dihydroxyflavanone, m.p. 182 °C (Lit.⁹ m.p. 180 °C); Acetate : compd. F + Ac₂O + Py, m.p. 144 °C (Lit.⁸ m.p. 144 °C); ¹H NMR (δ , CDCl₃) : 7.26 (1H, dd, *J* 7.5, 2.5 Hz, H-6'), 7.15 (1H, d, *J* 7.5, 2.5 Hz, H-2'), 7.01 (1H, *J* 7.5 Hz, H-5'), 6.46 (1H, *J* 2.5 Hz, H-8), 6.31 (1H, *J* 2.5 Hz, H-6), 3.87 (6H, s, 2 \times OMe), 2.70–5.50 (9H, m, 2 C-ring H, 7 glu H), 2.38 (3H, s, OAc), 2.32 (3H, s, OAc), 2.09 (3H, s, OAc), 2.07 (3H, s, OAc), 2.07 (3H, s, OAc), 2.06 (3H, s, OAc).

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